

Empirical Analysis of Obstructions to Women's Electoral Representation in Mardan District (Pakistan): A Case Study of the 2018 General Elections

Safia Ali, Farmanullah, Iltaf Khan, Naila Alam, Rowaid Khan

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 01, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: September 02, 2022</p> <p>Keywords : Electoral representation, district Mardan, general elections 2018, Voting gender gap, Factors of representation.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7041927</p>	<p><i>This research examines the factors impeding women's representation in elections in Mardan district (Pakistan) in relation to the 2018 general elections. The study has identified many factors such as conservative Pakhtun culture, narrow interpretation of religion, economic dependence of women, women's lack of interest in politics, lack of family cooperation, women's family responsibilities, lack of political awareness and lack of education identified. The study is qualitative and its scope is limited to Mardan district. The data were collected through a questionnaire in Mardan District from 400 respondents using convenience sampling. Data were analyzed using frequency, percent, and chi-square tests. The data were further elaborated using various independent variables such as area, gender, age and literacy.</i></p>

Introduction

Electoral representation is the electoral process in which the public elect their representatives, as evidenced by national legislature elections. The elected representatives have the power to select other representatives such as presidents or other office holders (Loeper, 2016: 180). It is the formal process of electing a person to public office or accepting or rejecting political opinions by voting. (Paul David Webb). The concept of representation is mainly that people represent other people, which is basically a modern one. The ancient Greeks had no equivalent term, although they elected some officials and sometimes sent ambassadors on activities; we can say that these activities are involved in representatives (Larsen, 1955). The Romans used the word *repraesentare*, and our own representation was determined by this Old French word, but they used it in the literal sense of bringing something that did not exist before. They didn't associate it with people acting on behalf of others or their political institutions. This usage appeared in Latin in the 13th and 14th centuries, and later in English, because people were sent to the Council of Churches or the British Parliament and gradually recognized as representatives (Patkin, 1967: 3).

Considering the significance of the notion, and the frequency with which political writers use it, there is little discussion or analysis of its meaning. Perhaps it is one of those basic concepts that are taken for granted that they themselves evade scrutiny; or its complexity hinders analysis. Hobbes was the only major political theorist who gave a comprehensive and logical explanation of its meaning; the opinions of other theorists should be obtained from random comments or read between the lines. Even John Stuart Mill, who dedicated the entire book to representative government, did not think that explaining what representative system was or what it meant was essential (Mill, 1874: 175-393).

However, the literature is full of obvious differences in meaning. The definitions proposed by some theorists directly contradict the definitions provided by others, or (even worse) have nothing to do with them. Few people attempt to explain these puzzling differences, so discussion of representation is riddled with long-standing controversies that seem to have no resolution. For example, Hobbes believes that every government is a representative government because it represents its subjects. On the other hand, the trend of this century is to criticize the so-called representation of indirect democracy as legendary or illusory. The author points out that all governments use propaganda to confront their problems, on the contrary, even autocratic dictators have popular support. They argue that there is no true representative of the government and that the true representative government does not exist. Another nagging and seemingly endless dispute involves proper relation between representative and constituents. Hobbes suggested that representatives are free to do whatever they want (at least as far as his voters are concerned). Most theorists claim that the representative should do his best for the person responsible for him, but should use his own judgment and wisdom to do what he thinks is best, because he was chosen to be (that is, not) your voter. However, some people insist that a representative's

duty is to accurately reflect the representative's wishes and opinions. They think that everything else is a mockery of the royal representatives (Cavell, 1958: 179).

Finally, claiming to choose one correct definition would not explain the timeless quality of the theorists' controversy, the unresolved and repetitive method. Instead, we can conclude that the representation has no fixed meaning, and that various theorists are actually talking about something else, so they disagree. Early writers disagree with late writers, probably because the concept has evolved. Or, if the meaning is not fixed, each writer is free to use the concept as needed and assign the selected meaning (Cavell, 1958: 172-212).

Electoral representation can be broadly divided into three sections: the right to elect, the right to participate in politics, and the right to gender-sensitive political decision-making process (Delys, 2014: 15). Representation of women in decision making and legal processes is seen as an important step towards women empowerment. Unfortunately, women make up half of the world's population, but they occupied only one-fifth participation in the legislature. In developed and underdeveloped countries, women's participation is under-represented (Hussain, 2016: 192).

According to Hernes, many arguments have been done about women's political representation and their participation, and in response to this, there are three main arguments.

The first argument states that representation of women is a democratic and fair issue, so, every group in society has the right to take part in such decisions which will in turn affect them. Half of the world's population is covered by women, hence they should be represented. This is neither the qualifications of those who make such decision nor the influence of their abilities on the quality of decision-making, but the participation of women is a democratic right.

The second argument asserts that if women do not participate in politics, society will fail because women's understanding of values and experience is different from that of men, so that both the gender needs to compete in order to make favorable decisions for society. In fact, an important factor is to involve women in the process of decision-making, as male decision-makers can forget, ignore, or ignore the impact of political decisions on women. If women are allowed to participate in politics, then it will probably change the meaning, conditions, and quality of decision-making because they belong to a separate gender experience as compare to men. This requires creating a broad decision-making space that is most suitable for all citizens from different perspectives. The entry of women into politics usually increases the skill level and demonstrates some important and valuable experience. This statement sees that women being absent from research and teaching as well as from politics as a waste of important experience, and this is the reason why women should also be the decision-makers with men, and not just acting as consumers.

The third argument shows that both men and women have different views and interests. The interest of women are not fully represented, suppressed or ignored. In the political system, there are conflicts among men and women, between suppressed and dominant values. Women must participate on an equal basis with men in order to make the conflicts between them visible. This will increase the degree of conflict in the short term, but it will lead to changes in the interests of women in the political system. But enduring, the political system will be less complicated. Hence, it is important to involve women in politics because they should focus on the political interests of women and not only on managing the problems that their interests have less value alongside men's interests (Hernes, 1987: 22).

RESEARCH QUESTION

What are the factors that affect the women's electoral representation in District Mardan with reference to 2018 General Elections?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research is to explore the factors of gender gap about women's electoral representation in 2018 General Elections in District Mardan. This study also emphasizes the responsibilities of women politicians in the decision-making process and the possible obstacles they face.

Quantitative Method

This study is based on a quantitative method. The primary data was collected through a questionnaire from the public in Mardan District.

Universe of the Study

The scope of the study is District Mardan. The sampling frame of the quantitative approach is male and female registered voters of District Mardan. The total number of registered voters in District Mardan is 1,239,067 whereas male registered voters are 719,872 and female registered voters are 520,067.

Sampling Size

Sample size has chosen by applying the taro Yamane's Formula. The sample size is 400 respondents have taken through taro Yamane's Formula out of the total of 1,239,067 registered voters of District Mardan. Taro Yamane's Formula, (1967) is as under:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where

“n” is the sample size.

“N” is the total population of the study.

“e” is the margin error i.e. equal to (.05).

$$n = 1,239,067 / 1 + 1,239,067 (.05)^2$$

$$n = 1,239,067 / 1 + 1,239,067 (0.0025)$$

$$n = 1,239,067 / 1,239,068 (0.0025)$$

$$n = 1,239,067 / 3,097.67$$

$$n = 399.99$$

$$n = 400$$

Hence, a sample size of 400 respondents has taken from District Mardan. Respondents were selected by convenience sampling from different categories as follows:

Category	Respondents from Urban		Respondents from Rural		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Illiterate	50	50	50	50	200
Literate	50	50	50	50	200
Total	100	100	100	100	400

Questionnaire

For the collection of data, questionnaire has been used as a tool. It consists of several open and close-ended questions that measured on 5-Points Likert Scale.

Analysis of Data:

The data has been analyzed through SPSS software. It comprised of descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) and inferential statistics (Chi-square test and p-value).

FACTORS AFFECTING WOMEN'S ELECTORAL REPRESENTATION IN DISTRICT MARDAN WITH REFERENCE TO 2018 GENERAL ELECTIONS: DATA ANALYSIS

This study has analyzed all those factors that affect women's electoral representation in District Mardan with reference to 2018 General Elections. The concept of women's electoral representation was analyzed and evaluated through various close ended questions. Firstly, general questions were asked in order to know about the general perception of people towards women's electoral representation in District Mardan. Further questions have been asked mostly related to various factors which will clearly indicate the gender gap of women's electoral representation in District Mardan with reference to 2018 General Elections. Percentages and frequencies have been calculated for all questions. Each of these questions has further analyzed by numerous independent variables i.e. urban/rural, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Women's Representation at National and Local Level

In order to find out the degree of awareness of people about women's electoral representation on national and local government level, in this context, the answers were collected to the question, "Are you aware about women's 17% quota in National and provincial legislatures and 33% quota in local government level?" People were asked to learn about the perception of women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 1: shows Women's Representation at National and Local Level

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Yes	No	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	58 (14.5%)	141 (35.3%)	200 (50.0%)	1.281	0.734
	Rural	53 (13.3%)	145 (36.3%)	200 (50.0%)		
	Total	111 (27.8%)	286 (71.5%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	57 (14.3%)	141 (35.5%)	200 (50.0%)	3.137	0.371
	Female	54 (13.5%)	145 (36.3%)	200 (50.0%)		
	Total	111 (27.8%)	286 (71.5%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	84 (21.0%)	167 (41.8%)	253 (63.3%)	15.063	0.020
	31-50 Years	17 (4.3%)	98 (24.5%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	10 (2.5%)	21 (5.3%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	111 (27.8%)	286 (71.5%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	93 (23.3%)	107 (26.8%)	200 (50%)	71.802	0.000
	Illiterate	18 (4.5%)	179 (44.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	111 (27.8%)	286 (71.5%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

According to the above table, it mentions that to some extent of rural as well as female respondents (36.3%) responded that they are not aware about women's 17% quota in National and provincial legislatures and 33% quota in local government level. Likewise, the respondents having the age group from 18-30 years (41.8%) and illiterate (44.8%) also gave similar response.

Lastly, it is revealed that majority of the respondents from rural areas, female respondents, age group from 18-30 years and illiterate clearly negated about the recognition of 17% women's quota in national and provincial assemblies and 33% quota in local government level.

Women's Quota in Assemblies

Women's quota in legislatures has been highly effective in representing gender interests. It is, therefore very important to find out the behavior of people towards the current reservation of women in assemblies. In this respect, answers were collected with regard to the question, "The 17% women quota in National and provincial legislatures is significant". People were asked to know about the perception regarding women's quota in assemblies. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 2: shows Women's Quota in Assemblies

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	51 (12.8%)	73 (18.3%)	58 (14.5%)	13 (3.3%)	5 (1.3%)	200 (50%)	9.889	0.042
	Rural	28 (7.0%)	88 (22.0%)	70 (17.5%)	11 (2.8%)	3 (0.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	79 (19.8%)	161 (40.3%)	128 (32.0%)	24 (6.0%)	8 (6.0%)	400(100)		
Gender	Male	43 (10.8%)	89 (22.3%)	53 (13.3%)	9 (2.3%)	6 (1.5%)	200 (50%)	9.697	0.046
	Female	36 (9.0%)	72 (18.0%)	75 (18.8%)	15 (3.8%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	79 (19.8%)	161 (40.3%)	128 (32.0%)	24 (6.0%)	8 (2.0%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	63 (15.8%)	98 (24.5%)	72 (18.0%)	17 (4.3%)	3 (0.8%)	253 (63.3%)	16.208	0.040
	31-50 Years	11 (2.8%)	51 (12.8%)	45 (11.3%)	5 (1.3%)	4 (1.0%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	5 (1.3%)	12 (3.0%)	11 (2.8%)	2 (0.5%)	1 (0.3%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	79 (19.8%)	161 (40.3%)	128 (32.0%)	24 (6.0%)	8 (2.0%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	56 (14.0%)	85 (21.3%)	38 (9.5%)	14 (3.5%)	7 (1.8%)	200 (50%)	40.580	0.000
	Illiterate	23 (5.8%)	76 (19.0%)	90 (22.5%)	10 (2.5%)	1 (0.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	79 (19.8%)	161 (40.3%)	128 (32.0%)	24 (6.0%)	8 (2.0%)	400(100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table shows that a limited number of rural respondents (22%) and male participants (22.3%) affirmed that 17% women's quota in National and Provincial legislature is significant. While, (24.5%) respondents having age from 18-30 years and (21.3%) of literate respondents followed in the same way. But a considerable number of illiterate people (22.5%) asserted that they have no idea about the standpoint.

To conclude, it was revealed that majority of respondents belonging to rural areas, male respondents, age group from 18-30 years and literate respondents greatly agreed with the point of view of 17% women's quota in national and provincial assemblies are noteworthy.

Women's Quota in Local Government System

Local government system also plays a vital role in gender inequality and in emerging the capabilities of women. It is, therefore very important to determine the perception of people towards women's quota in local government system. In this regard, responses were collected about this question, "The 33% women quota in local government system is significant". People were asked, so that to know about women's quota in local government system. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 3: shows Women's Quota in Assemblies

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	32 (8.0%)	75 (18.8%)	66 (16.5%)	20 (5.0%)	7 (1.8%)	200 (50%)	1.036	0.904
	Rural	28 (7.0%)	83 (20.8%)	64 (16.0%)	20 (5.0%)	5 (1.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	60 (15.0%)	158 (39.5%)	130 (32.5%)	40 (10.0%)	12 (3.0%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	30 (7.5%)	90 (22.5%)	52 (13.0%)	19 (4.8%)	9 (2.3%)	200 (50%)	11.363	0.023
	Female	30 (7.5%)	68 (17.0%)	78 (19.5%)	21 (5.3%)	3 (0.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	60 (15.0%)	158 (39.5%)	130 (32.5%)	40 (10.0%)	12 (3.0%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	42 (10.5%)	102 (25.5%)	71 (17.8%)	31 (7.8%)	7 (1.8%)	253 (63.3%)	12.105	0.147
	31-50 Years	13 (3.3%)	45 (11.3%)	49 (12.3%)	5 (1.3%)	4 (1.0%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	5 (1.3%)	11 (2.8%)	10 (2.5%)	4 (1.0%)	1 (0.3%)	31 (7.8%)		
Education	Total	60 (15.0%)	158 (39.5%)	130 (32.5%)	40 (10.0%)	12 (3.0%)	400 (100%)	42.561	0.000
	Literate	42 (10.5%)	82 (20.5%)	39 (9.8%)	26 (6.5%)	11 (2.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Illiterate	18 (4.5%)	76 (19.0%)	91 (22.8%)	14 (3.5%)	1 (0.3%)	200 (50%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table mentions that limited number of rural respondents (20.8%) and (22.5%) of male respondents stated that 33% women's quota in local government system is significant. Similarly, (25.5%) of respondents having age from 18-30 years and (20.5%) of literate respondents also maintained the same point of view. Whereas, some of the illiterate respondents (22.8%) affirmed that they are not aware about the viewpoint.

To conclude, it was establish that most of the respondents belonging to rural areas, male respondents, age group from 18-30 years and literate respondents greatly agreed with the point of view of 33% women's quota in local government system is significant.

Importance of Women Representation in Society

Women's representation in all spheres of life is important. They can raise the voice for women issues. It is, therefore very important to find out the views of people regarding women's electoral representation. In this context, the answers were collected to the question, "Women representation can speaks for women issues in society?" People were asked to learn about the perception of women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 4: shows Importance of Women Representation in Society

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	75 (18.8%)	94 (23.5%)	7 (1.8%)	17 (4.3%)	7 (1.8%)	200 (50%)	3.469	0.483
	Rural	72 (18.0%)	104 (26.0%)	7 (1.8%)	15 (3.8%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	147 (36.8%)	198 (49.5%)	14 (3.5%)	32 (8.0%)	9 (2.3%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	64 (16.0%)	109 (27.3%)	5 (1.3%)	18 (4.5%)	4 (1.0%)	200 (50%)	6.230	0.183
	Female	83 (20.8%)	89 (22.3%)	9 (2.3%)	14 (3.5%)	5 (1.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	147 (36.8%)	198 (49.5%)	14 (3.5%)	32 (8.0%)	9 (2.3%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	103 (25.8%)	116 (29.0%)	10 (2.5%)	19 (4.8%)	5 (1.3%)	253 (63.3%)	9.596	0.295
	31-50 Years	36 (9.0%)	63 (15.8%)	4 (1.0%)	11 (2.8%)	2 (0.5%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	8 (2.0%)	19 (4.8%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (0.5%)	2 (0.5%)	31 (7.8%)		
Education	Total	147 (36.8%)	198 (49.5%)	14 (3.5%)	32 (8.0%)	9 (2.3%)	400 (100%)	11.032	0.026
	Literate	83 (20.8%)	93 (23.3%)	3 (0.8%)	14 (3.5%)	7 (1.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Illiterate	64 (16.0%)	105 (26.3%)	11 (2.8%)	18 (4.5%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		

Explanation and Results

According to the above table it shows that (26%) of rural respondents and (27.3%) of male respondents agreed that women representation can raise voice for women issues in society. In the same way, (29%) respondents having age from 18-30 years and (26.3%) of illiterate respondents followed the same response.

Thus, it come to the conclusion that the respondents from rural parts, male respondents, age group of 18-30 years and illiterate respondents agreed that women representation can raise voice for women issues in society. Thus, it proves that most of respondents prefer women in electoral politics.

Women's Electoral Representation and *Pardah* as A Barrier

In order to know about factors of gender gap in women's electoral representation, question was asked from the respondents during investigation. In this context, the answers were collected to the question, "*Pardah* is the impediment in the way of women's electoral representation?" People were asked to learn about the perception of women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 5: shows Women's Electoral Representation and *Pardah* as A Barrier

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	21 (5.3%)	50 (12.5%)	9(2.3%)	77 (19.3%)	43 (10.8%)	200 (50%)	8.043	0.090
	Rural	30 (7.5%)	53 (13.3%)	10 (2.5%)	52 (13.0%)	55 (13.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	51 (12.8%)	103 (25.8%)	19 (4.8%)	129 (32.3%)	98 (24.5%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	39 (9.8%)	69 (17.3%)	7 (1.8%)	51 (12.8%)	34 (8.5%)	200 (50%)	42.338	0.000
	Female	12 (3.0%)	34 (8.5%)	12 (3.0%)	78 (19.5%)	64 (16.0%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	51 (12.8%)	103 (25.8%)	19 (4.8%)	129 (32.3%)	98 (24.5%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	26 (6.5%)	58 (14.5%)	15 (3.8%)	87 (21.8%)	67 (16.8%)	253 (63.3%)	12.215	0.142
	31-50 Years	21 (5.3%)	36 (9.0%)	2 (0.5%)	31 (7.8%)	26 (6.5%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	4 (1.0%)	9 (2.3%)	2 (0.5%)	11 (2.8%)	5 (1.3%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	51 (12.8%)	103 (25.8%)	19 (4.8%)	129 (32.3%)	98 (24.5%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	19 (4.8%)	37 (9.3%)	12 (3.0%)	72 (18.0%)	60 (15.0%)	200 (50%)	19.478	0.001
	Illiterate	32 (8.0%)	66 (16.5%)	7 (1.8%)	57 (14.3%)	38 (9.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	51 (12.8%)	103 (25.8%)	19 (4.8%)	129 (32.3%)	98 (24.5%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table mentions that (19.3%) of urban respondents and (19.5%) of female respondents showed that they are not agree with the statement that *pardah* is the hurdle in the way of women's electoral representation. Likewise, (21.8%) of respondents having age from 18-30 years and (18%) of literate respondents also opposed the viewpoint. However, (17.3%) of the male respondents and 16.5% of illiterate respondents agreed with the consideration. It means that there is inconsistency in this consideration.

By concluding this question, it was establish that respondents from urban regions, female respondents, the age group of 18-30 years and literate respondents opposed that *pardah* is an impediment in the way of women's electoral representation. This shows that majority of respondents are disagreed with the standpoint.

Women's Electoral Representation and *Pakhtun* Culture as a Barrier

In order to identify about factors of gender gap in women's electoral representation, question was asked from the people during survey. In this context, the answers were collected to the question, "*Pakhtun* Culture is the barrier in the way of women's electoral representation?" People were asked to learn about the perception of women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 6: shows Women's Electoral Representation and *Pakhtun* Culture as a Barrier

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	34 (8.5%)	79 (19.8%)	14 (3.5%)	48 (12.0%)	24 (6.0%)	200 (50%)	6.027	0.304
	Rural	40 (10.0%)	71 (17.8%)	6 (1.5%)	53 (13.3%)	30 (7.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	74 (18.5%)	150 (37.5%)	20 (5.0%)	101 (25.3%)	54 (13.5%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	48 (12.0%)	83 (20.8%)	11 (2.8%)	39 (9.8%)	19 (4.8%)	200 (50%)	19.426	0.002
	Female	26 (6.5%)	67 (16.8%)	9 (2.3%)	62 (15.5%)	35 (8.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	74 (18.5%)	150 (37.5%)	20 (5.0%)	101 (25.3%)	54 (13.5%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	43 (10.8%)	90 (22.5%)	15 (3.8%)	69 (17.3%)	36 (9.0%)	253 (63.3%)	17.678	0.061
	31-50 Years	23 (5.8%)	47 (11.8%)	5 (1.3%)	26 (6.5%)	15 (3.8%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	8 (2.0%)	13 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (1.5%)	3 (0.8%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	74 (18.5%)	150 (37.5%)	20 (5.0%)	101 (25.3%)	54 (13.5%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	29 (7.3%)	64 (16.0%)	12 (3.0%)	57 (14.3%)	37 (9.3%)	200 (50%)	17.567	0.004
	Illiterate	45 (11.3%)	86 (21.5%)	8 (2.0%)	44 (11.0%)	17 (4.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	74 (18.5%)	150 (37.5%)	20 (5.0%)	101 (25.3%)	54 (13.5%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table shows that limited number of urban respondents (19.8%) and (20.8%) of male respondents asserted that *pakhtun* culture is a barrier in the way of women's electoral representation. Similarly, (22.5%) of respondents having age from 18-30 years and (21.5%) illiterate respondents remarked that *pakhtun* culture is a barrier in the way of women's electoral representation.

This question can be concluded, that a large number of respondents from urban regions, male respondents, age group of 18-30 years and illiterate respondents replied that *pakhtun* culture is an impediment in the way of women's electoral representation. This shows that majority of respondents are agreed with the stance.

Women's Electoral Representation and Religion as a Barrier

In order to identify about factors of gender gap in women's electoral representation, question was asked from the respondents during investigation. In this context, the answers were collected to the question, "Religion is the barrier in the way of women's electoral representation?" People were asked to learn about the perception of women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 7: shows Women's Electoral Representation and Religion as a Barrier

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	31 (7.8%)	55 (13.8%)	16 (4.0%)	63 (15.8%)	35 (8.8%)	200 (50%)	6.996	0.136
	Rural	26 (6.5%)	62 (15.5%)	18 (4.5%)	44 (11.0%)	50 (12.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	57 (14.3%)	117 (29.3%)	34 (8.5%)	107 (26.8%)	85 (21.3%)	400(100%)		
Gender	Male	37 (9.3%)	74 (18.5%)	19 (4.8%)	38 (9.5%)	32 (8.0%)	200 (50%)	27.924	0.000
	Female	20 (5.0%)	43 (10.8%)	15 (3.8%)	69 (17.3%)	53 (13.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	57 (14.3%)	117 (29.3%)	34 (8.5%)	107 (26.8%)	85 (21.3%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	29 (7.3%)	67 (16.8%)	26 (6.5%)	68 (17.0%)	63 (15.8%)	253 (63.3%)	15.616	0.048
	31-50 Years	20 (5.0%)	43 (10.8%)	6 (1.5%)	30 (7.5%)	17 (4.3%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	8 (2.0%)	7 (1.8%)	2 (0.5%)	9 (2.3%)	5 (1.3%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	57 (14.3%)	117 (29.3%)	34 (8.5%)	107 (26.8%)	85 (21.3%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	16 (4.0%)	45 (11.3%)	21 (5.3%)	64 (16.0%)	54 (13.5%)	200 (50%)	29.423	0.000
	Illiterate	41 (10.3%)	72 (18.0%)	13 (3.3%)	43 (10.8%)	31 (7.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	57 (14.3%)	117 (29.3%)	34 (8.5%)	107 (26.8%)	85 (21.3%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table mentions that a limited number of urban respondents (15.8%) denied the idea that religion is the hurdle in the way of women's electoral representation. Whereas, the male respondents (18.5%) agreed with the point of view. Correspondingly, (17%) of respondents having age from 18-30 years opposed that religion is not a barrier in the way of women's electoral representation. While, reasonable number of illiterate respondents (18%) mentioned that religion is a barrier in the way of women's electoral representation. This shows that there is discrepancy in remarks.

This question can be concluded, that there is contradiction in views of the respondents either both in urban/rural regions, male/female respondents, age group of 18-30 years and above 31 years and literate/illiterate respondents. This shows that majority of respondents have different opinion.

Women's Electoral Representation and Economic Dependency as a Barrier

In order to find out factors of gender gap in women's electoral representation, question was asked from the respondents during investigation. In this context, the answers were collected to the question, "Economic dependency is the barrier in the way of women's electoral representation?" People were asked to learn about the perception of women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 8: shows Women's Electoral Representation and Economic Dependency as a Barrier

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	38 (9.5%)	104 (26.0%)	20 (5.0%)	29 (7.3%)	9 (2.3%)	200 (50%)	1.584	0.812
	Rural	40 (10.0%)	112 (28.0%)	19 (4.8%)	22 (5.5%)	7 (1.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	78 (19.5%)	216 (54.0%)	39 (9.8%)	51 (12.8%)	16 (4.0%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	46 (11.5%)	111 (27.8%)	15 (3.8%)	23 (5.8%)	5 (1.3%)	200 (50%)	7.497	0.112
	Female	32 (8.0%)	105 (26.3%)	24 (6.0%)	28 (7.0%)	11 (2.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	78 (19.5%)	216 (54.0%)	39 (9.8%)	51 (12.8%)	16 (4.0%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	51 (12.8%)	131 (32.8%)	26 (6.5%)	35 (8.8%)	10 (2.5%)	253 (63.3%)	2.851	0.943
	31-50 Years	21 (5.3%)	68 (17.0%)	11 (2.8%)	11 (2.8%)	5 (1.3%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	6 (1.5%)	17 (4.3%)	2 (0.5%)	5 (1.3%)	1 (0.3%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	78 (19.5%)	216 (54.0%)	39 (9.8%)	51 (12.8%)	16 (4.0%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	33 (8.3%)	96 (24.0%)	27 (6.8%)	35 (8.8%)	9 (2.3%)	200 (50%)	17.610	0.001
	Illiterate	45 (11.3%)	120 (30.0%)	12 (3.0%)	16 (4.0%)	7 (1.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	78 (19.5%)	216 (54.0%)	39 (9.8%)	51 (12.8%)	16 (4.0%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table reveals that (28%) of rural respondents as well as (27.8%) of male respondents asserted that economic dependency is a barrier in the way of women's electoral representation. The same response is also followed by respondents who are age 18-30 years(32.8%) and (30%) of the illiterate respondents.

To conclude this question, a number of respondents from rural regions, male respondents, age group of 18-30 years and illiterate respondents responded that economic dependency is an obstacle in the way of women's electoral representation. This shows that majority of respondents are agreed with the standpoint.

Women's Electoral Representation and their Interest in Election

Interest in any field is playing a key role in all phenomenon. In order to know about the interest of women in elections, responses were collected with regard to the question, "Women are not interested to contest elections due to non-cooperation from family?" People were asked to learn about the factor of gender gap towards women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 9: shows Women's Electoral Representation and their Interest in Election

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	64 (16.0%)	103 (25.8%)	12 (3.0%)	16 (4.0%)	5 (1.3%)	200 (50%)	2.356	0.671
	Rural	65 (16.3%)	110 (27.5%)	8 (2.0%)	15 (3.8%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	129 (32.3%)	213 (53.3%)	20 (5.0%)	31 (7.8%)	7 (1.8%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	67 (16.8%)	103 (25.8%)	8 (2.0%)	17 (4.3%)	5 (1.3%)	200 (50%)	2.800	0.592
	Female	62 (15.5%)	110 (27.5%)	12 (3.0%)	14 (3.5%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	129 (32.3%)	213 (53.3%)	20 (5.0%)	31 (7.8%)	7 (1.8%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	85 (21.3%)	128 (32.0%)	15 (3.8%)	19 (4.8%)	6 (1.5%)	253 (63.3%)	8.921	0.349
	31-50 Years	31 (7.8%)	72 (18.0%)	4 (1.0%)	8 (2.0%)	1 (0.3%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	13 (3.3%)	13 (3.3%)	1 (0.3%)	4 (1.0%)	0 (0.0%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	129 (32.3%)	213 (53.3%)	20 (5.0%)	31 (7.8%)	7 (1.8%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	60 (15.0%)	101 (25.3%)	14 (3.5%)	19 (4.8%)	6 (1.5%)	200 (50%)	9.584	0.049
	Illiterate	69 (17.3%)	112 (28.0%)	6 (1.5%)	12 (3.0%)	1 (0.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	129 (32.3%)	213 (53.3%)	20 (5.0%)	31 (7.8%)	7 (1.8%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table mentions that considerable number of rural respondents (27.5%) as well as (27.5%) of female respondents confessed that women are not interested to contest elections due to non-cooperation from family. Similarly, (32%) of respondents who are 18-30 years old and (28%) of illiterate respondents responded in the same manner.

By concluding this, it is assumed that majority of respondents from rural regions, female respondents, age group of 18-30 years and illiterate respondents responded that women are not interested to contest elections due to non-cooperation from family. This shows that majority of respondents are agreed with the viewpoint.

Women's Electoral Representation and their Interest in Elections

In order to know about the deliberation of women in politics, the answers were collected to the question, "Women are not interested to contest elections due to fulfilling family responsibilities?" People were asked to learn about the factor of gender gap towards women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 10: shows Women's Electoral Representation and their Interest in Elections

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	63 (15.8%)	94 (23.5%)	12 (3.0%)	23 (5.8%)	8 (2.0%)	200 (50%)	3.463	0.483
	Rural	75 (18.8%)	94 (23.5%)	11 (2.8%)	15 (3.8%)	5 (1.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	138 (34.5%)	188 (47.0%)	23 (5.8%)	38 (9.5%)	13 (3.3%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	67 (16.8%)	88 (22.0%)	14 (3.5%)	25 (6.3%)	6 (1.5%)	200 (50%)	5.835	0.212
	Female	71 (17.8%)	100 (25.0%)	9 (2.3%)	13 (3.3%)	7 (1.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	138 (34.5%)	188 (47.0%)	23 (5.8%)	38 (9.5%)	13 (3.3%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	88 (22.0%)	114 (28.5%)	12 (3.0%)	26 (6.5%)	13 (3.3%)	253 (63.3%)	10.415	0.237
	31-50 Years	38 (9.5%)	60 (15.0%)	9 (2.3%)	9 (2.3%)	0 (0.0%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	12 (3.0%)	14 (3.5%)	2 (0.5%)	3 (0.8%)	0 (0.0%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	138 (34.5%)	188 (47.0%)	23 (5.8%)	38 (9.5%)	13 (3.3%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	59 (14.8%)	86 (21.5%)	16 (4.0%)	28 (7.0%)	11 (2.8%)	200 (50%)	22.539	0.000
	Illiterate	79 (19.8%)	102 (25.5%)	7 (1.8%)	10 (2.5%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	138 (34.5%)	188 (47.0%)	23 (5.8%)	38 (9.5%)	13 (3.3%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table mentions that (23.5%) of respondents either belongs to urban or rural areas have similar opinion. Likewise, (25%) of female respondents, (28.5%) who are 18-30 years old and (25.5%) of illiterate respondents agreed that women are not interested to contest elections due to fulfilling family responsibilities. This shows that most of respondents are agreed with the standpoint.

Women's Electoral Representation and their Interest in Elections

To identify the interest of women in politics, the answers were collected to the question, "Women are not interested to contest elections due to lack of interest in politics?" People were asked to learn about the gender gap towards women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 11: shows Women's Electoral Representation and their Interest in Elections

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	65 (16.3%)	91 (22.8%)	20 (5.0%)	16 (4.0%)	8 (2.0%)	200 (50%)	2.420	0.659
	Rural	55 (13.8%)	106 (26.5%)	19 (4.8%)	14 (3.5%)	6 (1.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	120 (30.0%)	197 (49.3%)	39 (9.8%)	30 (7.5%)	14 (3.5%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	62 (15.5%)	95 (23.8%)	19 (4.8%)	15 (3.8%)	9 (2.3%)	200 (50%)	1.551	0.818
	Female	58 (14.5%)	102 (25.5%)	20 (5.0%)	15 (3.8%)	5 (1.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	120 (30.0%)	197 (49.3%)	39 (9.8%)	30 (7.5%)	14 (3.5%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	75 (18.8%)	120 (30.0%)	26 (6.5%)	20 (5.0%)	12 (3.0%)	253 (63.3%)	5.634	0.688
	31-50 Years	35 (8.8%)	63 (15.8%)	9 (2.3%)	7 (1.8%)	2 (0.5%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	10 (2.5%)	14 (3.5%)	4 (1.0%)	3 (0.8%)	0 (0.0%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	120 (30.0%)	197 (49.3%)	39 (9.8%)	30 (7.5%)	14 (3.5%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	50 (12.5%)	93 (23.3%)	25 (6.3%)	20 (5.0%)	12 (3.0%)	200 (50%)	17.526	0.002
	Illiterate	70 (17.5%)	104 (26.0%)	14 (3.5%)	10 (2.5%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	120 (30.0%)	197 (49.3%)	39 (9.8%)	30 (7.5%)	14 (3.5%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table indicates that (26.5%) of the rural respondents and (25.5%) of female respondents accepted that women are not interested to contest elections due to lack of interest in politics. Similarly, (30%) of the respondents who are 18-30 years old and (26%) of the illiterate respondents also replied in the same way. Thus, most of the respondents agreed with the standpoint.

Lastly, it is discovered that majority of the people from rural areas, female respondents, age group from 18-30 years and illiterate clearly admitted that view of lack of interest of women in politics.

Women's Electoral Representation and their interest in Elections

To find out the awareness of women in politics, the answers were collected to the question, "Women are not interested to contest elections due to lack of awareness in politics?" People were asked to learn about the gender gap towards women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 12: shows Women's Electoral Representation and their interest in Elections

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	46 (11.5%)	104 (26.0%)	23 (5.8%)	23 (5.8%)	4 (1.0%)	200 (50%)	8.446	0.077
	Rural	58 (14.5%)	113 (28.3%)	10 (2.5%)	17 (4.3%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	104 (26.0%)	217 (54.3%)	33 (8.3%)	40 (10.0%)	6 (1.5%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	58 (14.5%)	104 (26.0%)	19 (4.8%)	15 (3.8%)	4 (1.0%)	200 (50%)	5.682	0.224
	Female	46 (11.5%)	113 (28.3%)	14 (3.5%)	25 (6.3%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	104 (26.0%)	217 (54.3%)	33 (8.3%)	40 (10.0%)	6 (1.5%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	69 (17.3%)	133 (33.3%)	21 (5.3%)	25 (6.3%)	5 (1.3%)	253 (63.3%)	2.639	0.955
	31-50 Years	27 (6.8%)	68 (17.0%)	9 (2.3%)	11 (2.8%)	1 (0.3%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	8 (2.0%)	16 (4.0%)	3 (0.8%)	4 (1.0%)	0 (0.0%)	31 (7.8%)		
Education	Total	104 (26.0%)	217 (54.3%)	33 (8.3%)	40 (10.0%)	6 (1.5%)	400 (100%)	13.404	0.009
	Literate	46 (11.5%)	100 (25.0%)	23 (5.8%)	27 (6.8%)	4 (1.0%)	200 (50%)		
	Illiterate	58 (14.5%)	117 (29.3%)	10 (2.5%)	13 (3.3%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		

Explanation and Results

According to the above table, it mentions that limited number of respondents from rural area (28.3%) as well as (28.3%) female respondents asserted that due to lack of awareness in politics, they do not participate in elections. Correspondingly, (33.3%) of the respondents who are 18-30 years old and (29.3%) of the illiterate respondents also responded in the same way. Hence, majority of the respondents are agreed with the standpoint. Finally, it can be concluded that majority of the respondents from rural areas, female respondents, age group from 18-30 years and illiterate clearly confessed the view of lack of awareness of women in politics.

Women's Electoral Representation and their interest in Elections

Education plays a pivotal role in every field of life. It is, therefore very important to identify the interest of women in representation. In this context, the answers were collected to the question, "Women are not interested to contest elections due to lack of education?" People were asked to learn about the gender gap towards women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 13: shows Women's Electoral Representation and their interest in Elections

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	53 (13.3%)	90 (22.5%)	13 (3.3%)	34 (8.5%)	10 (2.5%)	200 (50%)	3.506	0.477
	Rural	53 (13.3%)	101 (25.3%)	8 (2.0%)	33 (8.3%)	5 (1.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	106 (26.5%)	191 (47.8%)	21 (5.3%)	67 (16.8%)	15 (3.8%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	54 (13.5%)	98 (24.5%)	10 (2.5%)	31 (7.8%)	7 (1.8%)	200 (50%)	0.656	0.957
	Female	52 (13.0%)	93 (23.3%)	11 (2.8%)	36 (9.0%)	8 (2.0%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	106 (26.5%)	191 (47.8%)	21 (5.3%)	67 (16.8%)	15 (3.8%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	70 (17.5%)	116 (29.0%)	11 (2.8%)	45 (11.3%)	11 (2.8%)	253 (63.3%)	6.812	0.557
	31-50 Years	25 (6.3%)	62 (15.5%)	7 (1.8%)	19 (4.8%)	3 (0.8%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	11 (2.8%)	13 (3.3%)	3 (0.8%)	3 (0.8%)	1 (0.3%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	106 (26.5%)	191 (47.8%)	21 (5.3%)	67 (16.8%)	15 (3.8%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	50 (12.5%)	86 (21.5%)	14 (3.5%)	39 (9.8%)	11 (2.8%)	200 (50%)	9.636	0.047
	Illiterate	56 (14.0%)	105 (26.3%)	7 (1.8%)	28 (7.0%)	4 (1.0%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	106 (26.5%)	191 (47.8%)	21 (5.3%)	67 (16.8%)	15 (3.8%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table mentions that (25.3%) of rural respondents and (24.5%) of the male respondents affirmed that women are not interested to contest elections due to lack of education. In the same way, (29%) of respondents who are 18-30 years old and (26.3%) of illiterate respondents are agreed with the standpoint. It means that majority of respondents (47.8%) are agreed with the point of view.

To conclude, it was found that most of the respondents hailing to rural areas, male respondents, age group from 18-30 years and illiterate respondents greatly agreed with the point of view that women are not interested to contest elections due to lack of education.

Women's Electoral Representation In 2018 Elections and its Comparison with 2013 Elections

To investigate women's electoral representation in 2018 general elections with comparison to 2013 elections, the answers were collected to the question, "Women's electoral representation has increased in 2018 General Elections as compare to 2013 General Elections?" People were asked to learn about the perception of women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 14: shows Women's Electoral Representation In 2018 Elections and its Comparison with 2013 Elections

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	32 (8.0%)	77 (19.3%)	78 (19.5%)	11 (2.8%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)	6.211	0.184
	Rural	28 (7.0%)	61 (15.3%)	102 (25.5%)	7 (1.8%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	60 (15.0%)	138 (34.5%)	180 (45.0%)	18 (4.5%)	4 (1.0%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	32 (8.0%)	72 (18.0%)	85 (21.3%)	10 (2.5%)	1 (0.3%)	200 (50%)	2.305	0.680
	Female	28 (7.0%)	66 (16.5%)	95 (23.8%)	8 (2.0%)	3 (0.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	60 (15.0%)	138 (34.5%)	180 (45.0%)	18 (4.5%)	4 (1.0%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	44 (11.0%)	86 (21.5%)	110 (27.5%)	10 (2.5%)	3 (0.8%)	253 (63.3%)	7.036	0.533
	31-50 Years	10 (2.5%)	40 (10.0%)	58 (14.5%)	7 (1.8%)	1 (0.3%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	6 (1.5%)	12 (3.0%)	12 (3.0%)	1 (0.3%)	0 (0.0%)	31 (7.8%)		
	Total	60 (15.0%)	138 (34.5%)	180 (45.0%)	18 (4.5%)	4 (1.0%)	400 (100%)		
Education	Literate	34 (8.5%)	75 (18.8%)	77 (19.3%)	11 (2.8%)	3 (0.8%)	200 (50%)	7.755	0.101
	Illiterate	26 (6.5%)	63 (15.8%)	103 (25.8%)	7 (1.8%)	1 (0.3%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	60 (15.0%)	138 (34.5%)	180 (45.0%)	18 (4.5%)	4 (1.0%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

According to the above table, it shows that (25.5%) of rural respondents and (23.8%) of female respondents responded that they don't know about the advancement of women's electoral representation in 2018 general elections as compare to 2013 general elections. Whereas, the age group 18-30 years (27.5%) and (25.8%) of illiterate respondents maintained the same point of view.

To conclude this question, it was establish that most of the respondents hailing to rural areas, female respondents, age group from 18-30 years and illiterate respondents greatly lack political awareness because they didn't know about advancement of women electoral representation in 2018 general elections as compare to 2013 general elections.

Women's Electoral Representation and importance of Political Background

To understand the notion that strong political background is necessary for the better electoral representation. It is therefore, essential to highlight the importance of political background. In this context, the answers were collected to the question, "For women's electoral representation, it is important to have strong political background?" People were asked to learn about the perception of women's electoral representation in District Mardan. This question was analyzed across multiple variables such as urban rural subdivision, gender, age, and literacy-based.

Table 15: shows Women's Electoral Representation and importance of Political Background

Variable	Sub-category of Variable	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Chi-square	P-value
Area	Urban	68 (17.0%)	74 (18.5%)	30 (7.5%)	22 (5.5%)	6 (1.5%)	200 (50%)	4.724	0.317
	Rural	59 (14.8%)	93 (23.3%)	23 (5.8%)	22 (5.5%)	3 (0.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	127 (31.8%)	167 (41.8%)	53 (13.3%)	44 (11.0%)	9 (2.3%)	400 (100%)		
Gender	Male	67 (16.8%)	86 (21.5%)	24 (6.0%)	16 (4.0%)	7 (1.8%)	200 (50%)	7.058	0.133
	Female	60 (15.0%)	81 (20.3%)	29 (7.3%)	28 (7.0%)	2 (0.5%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	127 (31.8%)	167 (41.8%)	53 (13.3%)	44 (11.0%)	9 (2.3%)	400 (100%)		
Age	18-30 Years	91 (22.8%)	92 (23.0%)	28 (7.0%)	34 (8.5%)	8 (2.0%)	253 (63.3%)	17.721	0.023
	31-50 Years	28 (7.0%)	60 (15.0%)	19 (4.8%)	8 (2.0%)	1 (0.3%)	116 (29.0%)		
	Above 50	8 (2.0%)	15 (3.8%)	6 (1.5%)	2 (0.5%)	0 (0.0%)	31 (7.8%)		
Total	127 (31.8%)	167 (41.8%)	53 (13.3%)	44 (11.0%)	9 (2.3%)	400 (100%)			
Education	Literate	64 (16.0%)	82 (20.5%)	20 (5.0%)	28 (7.0%)	6 (1.5%)	200 (50%)	7.523	0.111
	Illiterate	63 (15.8%)	85 (21.3%)	33 (8.3%)	16 (4.0%)	3 (0.8%)	200 (50%)		
	Total	127 (31.8%)	167 (41.8%)	53 (13.3%)	44 (11.0%)	9 (2.3%)	400 (100%)		

Explanation and Results

The above table mentions that (23.3%) of the rural respondents and (21.5%) of the male respondents supported the idea that strong political background is crucial for women's electoral representation. Correspondingly, (23%) of respondents who are 18-30 years old and (21.3%) of the illiterate respondents remarked in the same way. This question can be concluded, that most of the respondents from rural regions, male respondents, the age group of 18-30 years and illiterate respondents responded that strong political background is important for women's electoral representation. This shows that majority of respondents are agreed with the stance.

MAJOR FINDINGS

The main findings of the study are as follows:

- A huge number of respondents 71.5% responded that they are not aware about women's 17% quota in National and provincial legislatures and 33% quota in local government level.
- An average number of respondents 40.3% asserted that 17% women's quota in National and Provincial legislature is significant.
- A number of respondents 39.5% agreed with the view that 33% women's quota in local government system is significant.
- A number of respondents 49.5% maintained that women representation can raise voice for women issues in society.
- A good number of respondents 32.3% specified that they are not agree with the idea of *pardah* as impediment in the way of women's electoral representation.
- An average number of the respondents 37.5% admitted that *pakhtun* culture is a barrier in the way of women's electoral representation.
- Most of the respondents 29.3% confessed the idea that religion is a barrier in the way of women's electoral representation.
- A large number of respondents 54% asserted that economic dependency is an obstacle in the way of women's electoral representation.
- A great number of respondents 53.3% responded that women are not interested to contest elections due to non-cooperation from family.
- An average number of respondents 47% agreed that women are not interested to contest elections due to fulfilling family responsibilities.
- A number of respondents 49.3% declared that women are not interested to contest elections due to lack of interest in politics.

- Great number of respondents 54.3% admitted the view that women are not interested to contest elections due to lack of political awareness.
- A significant number of respondents 47.8% stated that women are not interested to contest elections due to lack of education.
- Majority of the respondents 47% declared that they did not know about the advancement of women's electoral representation in 2018 general elections as compare to 2013 general elections.
- Most of the respondents 41.8% answered that strong political background is important for women's electoral representation.

CONCLUSION

The study is mainly focusing on the concept i.e. electoral representation in District Mardan. Regarding women's electoral representation, there are different factors that are responsible for gender gap in women's electoral representation. A number of people in District Mardan were of the opinion that *pakhtun* culture (37.5%), religion (29.3%) and economic dependency (54%) are the obstacles in the way of women's electoral representation. Besides that, women themselves are also responsible for gender gap because they did not take interest in politics due to non-cooperation from family (53.3%), fulfilling family responsibilities (47%), lack of political awareness (54.3%), lack of education (47.8%) and lack of their interest (49.3%) as well.

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Author Information

Safia Ali

Visiting Lecturer, Women University Swabi, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Farmanullah

Assistant Professor, Pakistan Study Centre, University of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

Iltaf Khan

Subject Specialist, Elementary and Secondary Education Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Naila Alam

PhD Scholar, Department of Pakistan Study Centre, University of Peshawar, KP, Pakistan.

Rowaid Khan

Lecturer in Pakistan Studies, Bacha Khan University Charsadda, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.
